

Racing Against Time: The Invisible Effect of Hurry-Up Syndrome on Aviation Accidents*

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Hurry-Up Syndrome Safety Culture Time Pressure Human Factors Aviation Industry</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 5 October 2025 Revised: 15 December 2025 Accepted: 21 December 2025</p>	<p>In the aviation industry, time pressure, operational efficiency, and performance expectations are among the critical factors that directly effect human factors. In this context, urgency, referred to in the literature as Hurry-up syndrome, is a significant psychological phenomenon that threatens flight safety by leading to perceptual narrowing, cognitive overload, and decision making errors. This study aims to examine the effect of Hurry-up syndrome on aircraft accidents and presents a case study of pilots, air traffic controllers, and aircraft maintenance technicians involved in aviation operations. This study, designed with a qualitative research approach, analyzes in detail the Comair Flight 5191, Linate Airport, and Helios Airways Flight 522 accidents, selected from national and international accident reports, using document analysis methods. The data were examined through thematic analysis within the framework of coding human errors, time pressure, communication interruptions, and prioritization errors. The findings demonstrate that Hurry-up syndrome triggers cognitive errors across all task areas, leading to misalignment of task priorities, communication breakdowns, and impaired risk perception. It also reveals that organizational-level performance expectations and cultural factors fuel the behaviors associated with Hurry-up syndrome. The study examines the relationship between human factors and safety culture from the perspective of Hurry-up syndrome. In this respect, it aims to contribute to the sustainability of safety performance in aviation by suggesting preventive strategies in the training, workload planning and time management processes of organizations.</p>

1. Introduction

The aviation industry, despite its reliance on high technology and stringent regulations, is a system characterized by human factors. Today's aviation operations place a significant psychological burden on employees due to intense time pressures, increasing flight schedules, and constant performance expectations. The Hurry-up syndrome that emerges under these conditions causes employees to exhibit behavioral tendencies such as speeding up decision making processes due to time constraints, misjudging task priorities, and losing situational awareness (Reason, 1997; Helmreich & Merritt, 2000).

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Hurry-up syndrome is receiving increasing attention in the literature as a concept that facilitates cognitive errors that specifically impact flight safety. The time pressure experienced by pilots, air traffic controllers, and aircraft maintenance technicians shapes not only individual performance but also organizational safety culture (Maurino et al., 2017). Reports from the National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) and the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) indicate that the hurrying behavior associated with Hurry-up syndrome plays a direct or indirect role in a significant portion of accidents (ICAO, 2020).

A review of the literature reveals that studies on Hurry-up behavior and time pressure focus on specific operational roles. Pilot-focused studies show that time pressure negatively effects decision making, leading to procedural omissions (Orasanu & Fischer, 1997; Wiegmann & Shappell, 2017); air traffic controller-focused studies indicate that time pressure due to air traffic congestion leads to decreased situational awareness and communication errors (Hilburn, 2004; Eurocontrol, 2010); and maintenance-focused studies show that on-time delivery leads to skipped control procedures and incomplete implementations (Hobbs & Williamson, 2002; Rankin et al., 2000). These studies suggest that time pressure in flight and ground operations stems solely from the roles of aviation personnel. However, a research gap has been identified where studies have not examined, in a comparative and integrated manner, how employees in different roles experience similar Hurry-up syndrome. This deficiency prevents an adequate understanding of the critical effect of Hurry-up syndrome, a cause of aircraft accidents, on aviation safety.

This study aims to fill the aforementioned literature gap by systematically examining the effect of Hurry-up syndrome on aircraft accidents through three key occupational groups. Although the selected accidents stem from diverse roles such as pilots, air traffic controllers, and maintenance technicians, they all share the common denominator of Hurry-up syndrome (ANSV, 2004; AAIASB, 2006; NTSB, 2007). In this respect, the study goes beyond pilot-focused approaches, developing a holistic perspective that considers the multi-faceted nature of time pressure in different operational roles within aviation. Furthermore, by evaluating the effects of Hurry-up syndrome on decision making quality, communication dynamics, and safety culture through aircraft accident analyses, the study offers recommendations for preventive measures that can be taken at the organizational level.

The significance of this research lies in highlighting that the Hurry-up syndrome is not merely an individual psychological condition, but also an organizational and cultural phenomenon. Accordingly, the study seeks to answer questions about how the time pressure associated with Hurry-up syndrome leads to similar or different errors across different operational roles, and how these errors contribute to the process of aircraft accidents. In this respect, the study emphasizes the need for thorough analysis of the invisible effect of Hurry-up syndrome in the practical application of Safety Management Systems (SMS). Furthermore, this study presents not the cause of errors in aircraft accidents, but rather the circumstances that trigger hurry. It is anticipated that the findings will contribute to the restructuring of flight safety training content, the development of time management strategies, and the strengthening of safety culture.

2. Theoretical Background

The Hurry-up syndrome is conceptually related to individuals working under time pressure tending to make hurry decisions and failing to effectively utilize their cognitive resources in this process. Within this framework, theories and models that contributed to the emergence of the concept are presented. Reason's Swiss Cheese Model (Reason, 1990) will be used to explain how individual errors affect the organization and the system. The Threat and Error Management Model (Helmreich et al., 1999) will be used to reveal how time pressure can transform into a threat of error and how it weakens error management. Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) will be used to demonstrate how Hurry-up syndrome affects employees' memory, attention, and decision making capacities.

2.1. The Concept and Psychological Foundations of Hurry-Up Syndrome

The Hurry-up syndrome is defined as a cognitive and behavioral impairment that occurs when individuals feel the need to complete a specific task in a short amount of time. Stress factors such as time pressure, fatigue, high task intensity, and performance expectations underlie this syndrome (Dekker, 2014). Due to these factors, the individual shortens their attention span, accelerates the decision making process, and reduces their risk perception. These behaviors manifest as automatic responses developed unconsciously by the employee to

complete the task (Helmreich and Merritt, 2000). The individual's attempt to simplify complex tasks weakens operational safety.

Psychologically, the Hurry-up syndrome is a result of cognitive stress due to time pressure. McEwen (2007: 882) states that this type of stress is associated with overactivity in the amygdala region of the brain at the neural level, which triggers quick but low-accuracy decisions. Time pressure increases the risk of error by leading individuals to make intuitive and shortcut decisions in the decision making process (Orasanu & Fischer, 1997). In sectors requiring high safety standards, such as aviation, this cognitive contraction can lead to chain reactions of errors. Furthermore, when group haste occurs through social interaction among individuals, this effect can spread throughout the organization (Reason, 1997).

One of the psychological phenomena arising from the Hurry-up syndrome is the distortion of risk perception and the tendency to deviate from standard behaviors. When shortening procedures and skipping certain controls due to time pressure do not yield negative consequences in the short term, such behaviors become acceptable at the micro level (Vaughan, 1996; Reason, 1997). In the long term, these behaviors lead to the accumulation of hidden errors, paving the way for accidents. According to Dekker (2014), such behaviors are generally not due to individual carelessness, but rather to the internalization of organizational pressure mechanisms by employees.

A review of studies in the literature reveals that the Hurry-up syndrome is not solely comprised of individual psychological tendencies, as described above, but is also related to organizational culture and performance management. Hobbs & Williamson (2002), in their study on aircraft maintenance technicians, found that organizational time pressure increased violations of checklists and procedural omissions. In another study, Wiegmann & Shappell (2017), using the Human Factors Analysis and Classification (HFACS) model, indicated that time pressure is a prerequisite for individual errors. These findings necessitate an examination of the psychological foundations of the Hurry-up syndrome within the framework of individual-organization interaction.

2.2. Human Factors and Time Pressure in Aviation

Due to the nature of aviation operations, human factors are central to the safety chain. ICAO (2020: 1-1-3) defines human factors as psychological, physiological, and social variables that affect people's interactions with their environment, vehicles, and other people. Among these variables, time pressure emerges as one of the strongest cognitive stressors. Furthermore, time pressure encountered in aviation operations is constantly amplified by organizational factors such as flight frequency, operational delay costs, and performance targets (Dekker, 2011). In this context, time pressure can be seen not only as an individual source of stress but also as a structural human factors problem arising from the system.

Empirical findings show that time pressure can manifest in different situations within the framework of human factors. Flin et al. (2008: 24) emphasize that time pressure leads to a loss of situational awareness in employees, causing an increase in risky behaviors. This situation, particularly prevalent in pilots, can create a time pressure error chain. The links in this chain rapid decision making, skipping errors, and lack of verification can break, leading to aircraft accidents. Air traffic controllers and aircraft maintenance technicians are similarly affected by time pressure. Maintenance technicians working under time pressure tend to make intuitive decisions rather than analytical decisions that require a specific evaluation process and more time (Çoban & Aydoğdu, 2020). However, this pressure can manifest in different ways. In controllers, it appears as workload and distraction, while in technicians, it is seen as time pressure and shift fatigue (Maurino et al., 2017). Therefore, the Hurry-up syndrome is not merely an individual tendency to accelerate; it also emerges as a multidimensional risk factor that creates a loss of synchronization between different components of the operational system.

From a human factors perspective, time pressure is not only a situation affecting individual performance, but also a phenomenon related to organizational culture and performance management understanding. Sustainable safety in aviation necessitates the design of a system that requires employees to fully implement procedures even when experiencing time pressure (Dekker, 2014). Therefore, innovative approaches to aviation safety emphasize the recognition, fair reporting, and management of time pressure (ICAO, 2018). Such an approach contributes to eliminating the dilemma between speed and safety.

2.3. Theoretical Basis for Hurry-Up Syndrome

The theoretical theories and models put forward to explain the Hurry-up syndrome will be examined in this section of the study.

2.3.1. Reason's Swiss Cheese Model

This model, developed by Reason (1990), explains accidents through the balance within a multi-layered defense system. Each layer possesses a defensive barrier capable of preventing error. According to this model, accidents occur when these defensive layers weaken simultaneously. The time pressure created by the syndrome, along with cognitive distraction, behavioral procedural omissions, and decreased control at the organizational level, can weaken the defenses of these layers. Therefore, the Hurry-up syndrome can be considered not only an individual behavioral tendency but also a systemic vulnerability.

The time pressure that arises from the Hurry-up syndrome initially leads to an imbalance between safety and efficiency at the organizational level. Managerial expectations such as increasing flights, shortening maintenance times, and reducing delay costs cause hidden conditions to emerge later (Dekker, 2011). Such decisions can create a situation that increases the likelihood of employees making mistakes. At the individual level, the Hurry-up syndrome transforms into active errors in the form of skipping procedures, failing to perform cross-checks, and engaging in non-standard practices. According to Reason's (1997) model, these types of errors are often not unusual but are fueled by behaviors created by the system.

In aviation operations, the pressure on pilots to take off quickly, the air traffic controller's efforts to provide hurry guidance, and the technician's tendency to shorten maintenance time actually weaken the function of defensive barriers. This model shows that behaviors arising from the Hurry-up syndrome can play both an active and latent role in the chain leading to an accident.

2.3.2. Threat and Error Management (TEM) Model

TEM is a model based on the management of threats, errors, and undesirable situations in aviation (ICAO, 2020). This model involves identifying threats encountered in aviation, managing the errors that lead to them, and preventing undesirable situations (Helmreich et al., 1999). The Hurry-up syndrome manifests itself as an operational threat in this model because the resulting time pressure can directly weaken employees' capacity to manage their errors.

The Hurry-up behaviors, driven by time pressure, can prolong the time it takes to detect potential errors (Maurino et al., 2017). Therefore, small errors made during operations may not be detected early and may grow within the system over time. This can lead to errors progressing undetected and the emergence of undesirable flight situations (Helmreich & Merritt, 2000). Thus, the Hurry-up syndrome can make it difficult to identify threats and manage errors within the framework of the TEM model.

The TEM approach offers a safety framework that is directly related to the principles of crew resource management (CRM). According to CRM principles, open communication among team members plays a significant role in feedback, overcoming hierarchical barriers, and early detection of errors (Salas et al., 2006). However, time pressure in environments experiencing Hurry-up syndrome can limit interaction within the team, hindering the proper functioning of the feedback mechanism.

2.3.3. Cognitive Load Theory

Cognitive load theory, proposed by Sweller (1988), suggests that an individual's work capacity is limited. Time pressure affects this capacity, leading to increased cognitive load. As a result, difficulties in processing complex information, hurry decision making, and weakened analytical thinking occur.

The Hurry-up syndrome causes cognitive overload, leading to a decrease in situational awareness. Situational awareness is a phenomenon consisting of three stages: perceiving data, interpreting it, and considering future situations (Endsley, 1995). Due to time pressure, the integrity between these stages of the process can be disrupted, resulting in a focus only on the immediate task and the overlooking of important matters.

Hurry-up syndrome, within the framework of this theory, can be considered a consequence of an overloaded decision making environment. The pilot's effort to hurry process the flow of information in the cockpit during flight, the air traffic controller's desire to successfully complete the communication process, or the maintenance technician's need to complete procedures within a limited time all create an overload on working

memory and can increase the likelihood of errors (Flin et al., 2008). Therefore, excessive cognitive load can lead employees to resort to procedural shortcuts and intuitive decision making processes.

2.4. The Relationship Between Safety Culture and Hurry-Up Syndrome

The Hurry-up syndrome is not only an individual cognitive response but also a behavioral pattern shaped within a safety culture. Safety culture is defined as the set of values that reveal individuals' risk perception and determine their safety behaviors within an organization (Guldenmund, 2000). Employees play a role in the transmission of safety culture from generation to generation by forming its links.

Studies in the literature show that time pressure is effective in the perceived power dimension of safety culture. Hofmann & Stetzer (1996) found that in organizations with high production demand, employees tended to skip safety procedures and increase their risk taking tendencies. In another study, Ek & Akseleson (2005) revealed that in organizations with speed and performance-oriented managerial expectations, employees did not exhibit safety related feedback and reporting behaviors. These findings may indicate that the Hurry-up syndrome is not only an individual attitude but also a behavioral condition shaped by organizational culture.

With the increase in flight demand, a race against time culture has become a part of operational performance metrics in many aviation companies. Indicators such as delays caused by aircraft departure, efficient air traffic management, and timely completion of maintenance create pressure on employees to hurry (Dekker, 2011). This pressure can negatively affect decision making processes, disrupting the balance between performance and safety and potentially relegating safety to a secondary priority (Çoban, 2019; Çapkulaç, 2025).

At the organizational level, factors contributing to the emergence of Hurry-up syndrome include operational timelines, penalties or performance based evaluations for delays, short shift durations, inadequate staff allocation, and a culture of punctuality (Dekker, 2014). The combination of these factors creates a tendency among employees to prioritize meeting deadlines over safety. Employees often internalize the pressure to be fast not only as a managerial expectation but also as an indicator of professional competence. Therefore, behavioral patterns that begin individually with Hurry-up syndrome can spread throughout the organization, weakening safety.

3. Methodology

The methods section of the study will present information on the research methodology used, data sources, and data analysis.

3.1. Research Method

This study is a qualitative research aimed at examining the effect of Hurry-up syndrome, experienced by pilots, air traffic controllers, and aircraft maintenance technicians involved in aviation operations, on aircraft accidents. Qualitative research aims to make sense of complex social phenomena within a specific context and to reveal the meanings behind these phenomena (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Qualitative research provides a suitable framework for examining a phenomenon like Hurry-up syndrome, which cannot be directly measured but can be observed through human behavior, organizational pressures, and cognitive processes.

The study utilized document analysis methods based on past accident reports and incident investigation records. This method involves systematically examining document contents to extract meaningful themes, patterns, and inferences (Bowen, 2009). It is particularly useful for examining data related to past events in situations where direct observation or interviews are not possible.

The document analysis method used in this study was applied by following a systematic process. The research process was carried out in four stages: (1) aircraft accident selection, (2) document review, (3) coding and theme creation, and (4) relating the findings to the theoretical framework. This staged structure aims to increase the transparency and reproducibility of the research.

3.2. Data Sources

The research's data sources consist of official national and international accident investigation reports and related academic literature. In this context, reports published by the National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB), the Italy National Flight Safety Board (ANSV), the Greece Aircraft Accident Investigation and Safety Board (AAIASB), the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), and the USA Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) were examined. These reports were chosen because they contain detailed information

not only on the technical aspects of aircraft accidents but also on individual human factors, operational conditions, and organizational processes.

A review of the literature revealed that there is no integrated study on Hurry-up syndrome and different actors in aviation. Nine accidents were examined, three for each actor. In this study, accident examples that represent each actor and can explain the theoretical basis of Hurry-up syndrome were included. These three (3) aircraft accidents; the pilot-focused Comair Flight 5191, the air traffic controller-focused Linate Airport, and the aircraft maintenance technician-focused Helios Airways Flight 522 accident were examined using an in depth qualitative analysis method. The limitation of the number of cases is based on the aim of conducting an in depth contextual analysis rather than the generalizability of the study. This approach is consistent with the nature of qualitative research and allows for the detailed analysis of complex human factor interactions (Patton, 2015). Accordingly, each accident was evaluated in a way that would show how Hurry-up syndrome manifests in different operational environments.

The accidents examined were selected using purposive sampling to represent different actors in aviation operations, including pilots, air traffic controllers, and maintenance technicians. Purposive sampling is an approach that focuses on selecting cases that are most relevant to the research objective and rich in information (Patton, 2015). The following criteria were considered in selecting the reports:

- Clearly defining the element of operational hurrying and time pressure in accident reports,
- Including human factors analyses in reports,
- Representation of different professional groups (pilot, controller, technician),
- Official documents being publicly available and verifiable.

These criteria have made it possible to examine the effects of Hurry-up syndrome experienced by employees in different roles within aviation operations.

3.3. Data Analysis

In the data analysis process, selected accident reports were first read holistically. Then, coding was performed, and the expressions in each line were analyzed and coded. In the coding process, indicators related to time pressure and hurry behaviors, found in the human factors literature, were used as the basis. These indicators include: procedural omissions, missing checklists, communication breakdowns, decision making errors, delay pressure, and productivity-focused performance expectations.

The Error codes, delay codes, and safety violation classifications included in official accident reports were used as an interpretive framework in the analysis process. Although these codes do not directly evoke the term Hurry-up syndrome, they were considered as indicators of human factors that indirectly reflect hurry behaviors. The Human Factors Analysis and Classification System (HFACS) and Threat and Error Management (TEM) perspectives were utilized in interpreting the codes.

The obtained codes were grouped according to their semantic similarities and transformed into main themes through thematic analysis. These themes were structured under three main categories: cognitive load and loss of situational awareness at the individual level; communication breakdown and deficiencies in team resource management at the crew level; and productivity pressure and time pressured performance indicators at the organizational level. The resulting themes allowed for a comparative evaluation of how Hurry-up syndrome manifests in different operational roles. These themes, included in the analysis process, were interpreted in relation to Reason's Swiss Cheese Model, the Threat and Error Management approach, and Cognitive Load Theory.

4. Findings and Discussion

The findings from the three accident reports studied, the effects of Hurry-up syndrome, the evaluation of the findings, and their interpretation within the context of the literature are presented below.

4.1. Pilot Case: Comair Flight 5191

Comair Flight 5191 crashed on the morning of August 27, 2006, while preparing for takeoff from Lexington Blue Grass Airport (LEX) in Kentucky, USA, to Atlanta, Georgia, USA. The Bombardier CRJ-100ER regional jet, operating the flight, veered off the runway during takeoff from the main runway at 06:06 and quickly burst into

flames, killing 49 of the 50 people on board (NTSB, 2007). Just before the accident, the crew diverted to the wrong runway (Runway 26) in darkness and low visibility. According to the accident report, the planned runway (Runway 22) was 2,133 meters long, while the runway the pilots mistakenly entered was only 1,067 meters long. This information may have prevented the aircraft from taking off. The factors contributing to this aircraft accident, the report findings, and the assessment of Hurry-up syndrome are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Comair Flight 5191 Aircraft Crash Analysis Findings and Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome

Impact Dimensions	Accident Findings	Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome
Operational Conditions	Early morning Low vision Presence of a single air traffic controller	Fatigue Lack of cognitive attention due to task intensity
Time Pressure Source	Obligation to take off on time Being the first flight of the day	Flight crew expedites procedures to avoid delays
Human Factors	Lack of communication Fatigue Low lighting conditions False perception of trust	Loss of situational awareness Formation of faulty decision chain
Procedural Errors	Failure to verify take-off runway identity Lack of cross-checking	Failure to complete the departure control process due to hurry behavior
Cognitive Factors	Attentional narrowing Increased decision making speed Decreased environmental awareness	Distraction from symptoms of Hurry-up syndrome
Organizational Factors	Presence of on-time departure performance Single air traffic controller application	Time pressure culture at the organizational level Expectation of punctuality

The analysis findings in Table 1 illustrate the effects of Hurry-up syndrome on the Comair Flight 5191 accident at the cognitive, operational, and organizational levels. It can be argued that the pilots, with the cognitive narrowing that is a symptom of Hurry-up syndrome, focused their attention solely on completing the takeoff, losing their environmental awareness. The accident demonstrates that time pressure can transcend individual performance errors and become a systemic vulnerability.

From a safety management perspective, the Comair 5191 accident can be viewed as a direct demonstration of the fatal consequences of Hurry-up syndrome when the culture of on-time takeoff and punctuality conflicts with the priority of safety. An examination of the accident report revealed that the flight crew, under pressure to meet the flight schedule, expedited the checklist and skipped the procedure for verifying the accuracy of the takeoff runway. This situation demonstrates that the goal of on-time take-off overrides flight safety, an example of Hurry-up syndrome.

In this pilot-related accident, time pressure can be said to have reduced decision making quality, increased cognitive load, and led to procedural deviations. This finding, consistent with Reason's (1990) human error model, suggests that Hurry-up syndrome can limit and superficialize cognitive resources. As a cognitive effect, pilots experienced a narrowing of their focus on completing their tasks, leading to a decrease in their environmental awareness. Furthermore, there appeared to be a lack of tacit approval and cross-checking in crew communication. This demonstrates that a culture of hurry can undermine healthy interaction within the cockpit.

The association of pilot error with Hurry-up syndrome can be attributed to a misjudgment of priorities and a delay in implementing necessary safety checks in the process leading to the accident. Accident findings indicate that the error stemmed not from a technical malfunction, but from cognitive processes compressed under time pressure. In this context, the Comair 5191 accident can be interpreted not only as individual inattention but also as a cognitive and organizational outcome of Hurry-up syndrome.

4.2. Air Traffic Controller Case: Linate Airport Accident

On October 8, 2001, at 08:09, an SAS Airlines aircraft, SK 686 Boeing MD-87, was approaching the runway for takeoff at Milan Linate Airport (Italy) when it struck a Cessna Citation CJ2 private jet that was traveling on a taxiway that should not have entered the runway intersection. Both aircraft exploded in the accident, killing 118 people (ANSV, 2004). According to the accident report, visibility at the airport was reduced to approximately 200 meters due to dense fog. This visibility may have prevented aircraft taxiing to the runway from seeing each other. The factors contributing to the aircraft accident, the report findings, and an assessment of the Hurry-up syndrome are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Linate Airport Accident Analysis Findings and Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome

Impact Dimensions	Accident Findings	Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome
Operational Conditions	Drizzling Radar system is off Morning flight traffic density Presence of a single air traffic controller	Workload Environmental stress factors causing time pressure
Time Pressure Source	Pressure to avoid departure delays Increased flight frequency Insufficient staff	Air traffic controller bypassing verification processes to speed up procedures
Human Factors	Distraction Information overload Lack of visual confirmation	The formation of cognitive narrowing
Procedural Errors	Failure to verify taxi route Radar system not activated	Disabling safety barriers due to hasty behavior
Organizational Factors	Staff shortage Inadequate technical systems Operational time pressure	Time pressure culture at the organizational level

The analysis findings in Table 2 illustrate the cognitive and organizational effects of time pressure on the air traffic controller in the Linate Airport accident, stemming from Hurry-up syndrome. It can be argued that the air traffic controller's Hurry-up syndrome symptoms led to decision making errors. The accident also demonstrates that a culture of time pressure can be a direct consequence of organizational time pressure. It demonstrates that the controller's hurry behavior, combined with systemic conditions, can create a chain reaction of multiple errors. In this accident, Hurry-up syndrome manifested not only as an individual but also as a systemic form of Hurry-up pressure. While attempting to manage the increasing traffic density on his own, the air traffic controller, in his tendency to accelerate his workflow, bypassed verification processes.

In this accident, which was caused by an air traffic controller, it can be argued that time pressure may have increased cognitive load and reduced error perception. Furthermore, organizational factors such as the ineffective use of radar systems and staff shortages necessitated the necessity of keeping everything on schedule for the completion of the task. The accident findings demonstrate that Hurry-up syndrome can occur not only individually but also in organizational structures and crew resource management. This emerging situation finds its place in the concept of hidden hidden conditions defined by ICAO in its Human Factors Training Manual (2020).

The connection between this air traffic controller-related accident and the Hurry-up syndrome lies in the fact that errors caused by actors exhibiting different roles converge under a common denominator of time pressure. The concerns about delays expressed in the accident report, the high volume of traffic, and expectations regarding maintaining operational flow triggered the process that led to the accident. In this context, the Linate airport accident can be seen as a case study demonstrating the impact of Hurry-up syndrome on the system.

4.3. Aircraft Maintenance Technician Case: Helios Airways Flight 522

On August 14, 2005, at 12:03 PM, a Helios Airlines Boeing 737-31S, operating a flight from Larnaca (Cyprus) to Athens (Greece) to Prague (Czechia), crashed in the Grammatiko area near Athens, Greece. The accident,

which occurred due to fuel exhaustion, resulted in the deaths of 121 people (AAIASB, 2006). The accident report states that shortly after takeoff, the aircraft experienced a loss of cabin pressure during climb due to a malfunction in the automatic cabin pressurization system. The flight crew, unable to verify the accuracy of the system warnings, suffered hypoxia, and the pressure loss caused oxygen deprivation, rendering them incapacitated. The factors contributing to the aircraft accident, the report findings, and an assessment of Hurry-up syndrome are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Helios Airways Flight 522 Aircraft Crash Analysis Findings and Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome

Impact Dimensions	Accident Findings	Relationship with Hurry-Up Syndrome
Operational Conditions	Pressurization system leak test Shift change pressure	Shortening procedural steps to motivate quick task completion
Time Pressure Source	Cycle time constraints Program durations End of shift	Failure to set the selector switch to AUTO mode after the cabin pressure test Failure to follow the checklist
Human Factors	Maintenance restore error Misinterpretation of warnings in the cockpit Exposure to hypoxia	Cognitive contraction under load Failure to apply the cross-check list
Procedural Errors	Not setting the pressure mode selector to AUTO Lack of independent control	Rush completion No verification
Design / Ergonomics Factor	The cabin altitude warning system and the takeoff configuration warning system have the same sound	Making the wrong decision due to difficulty in diagnosing the warning
Organizational Factors	Procedural standard Lack of aftercare control culture	Time pressure culture Weakening of security barriers

The analysis findings in Table 3 indicate that the time pressure experienced by the aircraft maintenance technician during the maintenance process, stemming from the Hurry-up syndrome, eliminated the restoration and verification steps. The technician's desire to complete the task quickly could have led to incomplete or non-implemented procedures. This accident demonstrates that a culture of on-time delivery in maintenance organizations leads to shortened procedures, omission of steps, and incomplete documentation. Furthermore, it indicates that these behaviors, when combined with conditions that challenge human performance limitations, such as hypoxia, during flight operations, can lead to accidents and crashes. It was determined that after a cockpit pressure test performed near the end of a shift, the maintenance technician failed to return the system selector switch to the AUTO position and document this change in the shift transfer file. This situation demonstrates an example of procedure skipping due to time pressure.

In this accident, which involved an aircraft maintenance technician, anxiety about finishing the shift may have led to a job-focused acceleration behavior. This accident finding demonstrates the micro-implication of the Hurry-up syndrome described by Dekker (2014) in maintenance environments. Furthermore, at the organizational level, short maintenance planning cycle times and the prominent on-time delivery culture support the systemic nature of the syndrome. This situation demonstrates that rushing behavior can have fatal consequences not only during flight but also in the maintenance hangar.

The connection between this aircraft maintenance technician-related accident and the Hurry-up syndrome lies in the fact that time constraints create shared pressure on decision making and execution for both maintenance technicians and pilots. Skipping procedures, lack of cross-checking, and technical confusion can be said to have contributed to the accident. In this context, the Helios accident can be seen as highlighting the Hurry-up syndrome, a safety risk affecting both maintenance and flight operations.

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

This study examines the effects of Hurry-up syndrome on safety culture in aviation operations from a human factors perspective, using accident reports caused by three different actors. The aircraft accident findings indicate that pilots, air traffic controllers, and maintenance technicians, despite their different operational roles, are exposed to Hurry-up syndrome due to similar cognitive and behavioral characteristics. The findings reveal that time pressure is a systemic risk factor that directly affects both individual decision-making processes and organizational functioning.

The findings of this study support the findings in the human factors literature regarding the negative effect of Hurry-up syndrome on the cognitive processes of employees working under time pressure. Hobbs (2008) and Wickens et al. (2015) state in their studies that time pressure weakens situational awareness and leads individuals to make superficial decisions. The checklist violations, prioritization errors, and communication deficiencies observed in the aircraft accidents examined are consistent with the findings of previous research. While this study presents findings that support the existing literature, it also expands on the literature in some important aspects. While previous research focused on the impact of time pressure on individual performance (Hancock & Warm, 1989; Hobbs, 2008), this research reveals the effect of Hurry-up syndrome on crew interaction and safety culture through concrete accident examples.

An examination of empirical research in the literature reveals that Hurry-up syndrome is mostly addressed through a single operational role (Hancock & Warm, 1989; Endsley & Rodgers, 1998; Wickens & Hollands, 2000; Reason & Hobbs, 2003; Hobbs, 2008). This study aims to fill this gap in the literature by presenting a multi-actor and system-level analysis that includes pilots, air traffic controllers, and maintenance technicians. It can be argued that in accidents caused by air traffic controllers and maintenance technicians, the Hurry-up behavior may not only be individual but also stem from a failure to meet organizational expectations and operational pace.

The three accident examples examined demonstrate that organizational time management deficiencies lie at the root of the Hurry-up syndrome. In the pilot-related accident, the pressure to take off on time; in the air traffic controller-related accident, the workload and staff shortages in the tower due to flight frequency; and in the aircraft maintenance technician-related accident, shift handover times, all relegated safety to a secondary priority. This process involves the hidden and invisible organizational failure described by Reason (1997). Furthermore, the Hurry-up syndrome is not only a behavioral tendency but also a cultural symptom. It arises when the organization's speed, efficiency, and performance indicators become more dominant than safety principles. This cultural structure can hinder both individual awareness and healthy communication.

Employees performing their duties under time pressure experience cognitive contraction, distraction, and weakened risk perception. Pilots, controllers, and technicians, who are actors in aviation operations, become less aware of their surroundings while focusing on completing their tasks (Flin et al., 2008). This cognitive process constitutes a serious breaking point in terms of safety management. In this context, it can be stated that speed is the greatest enemy of safety and leads to a chain reaction of errors. A strong safety culture, as emphasized by Guldenmund (2000), is based on a value system that prioritizes safety over speed, profit, or efficiency. The accidents examined in this study show that the Hurry-up syndrome disrupts the system, revealing similar cognitive and behavioral patterns from the cockpit to the hangar.

At the organizational level, performance indicators such as on-time departure, punctuality, and cycle time create an invisible norm of speed and a drive to succeed among employees. This situation triggers hurry behavior at the individual level. In this context, the sustainability of a safety culture can only be achieved through the restructuring of organizational values. Training programs in team, group, and maintenance resource management should include the identification of factors that trigger the Hurry-up syndrome and steps to effectively manage this process. By allowing time flexibility in task planning, operational delays can be considered non-safety breaches, and deviations can be accepted as natural, making this a part of the organizational culture. Redefining performance indicators, ensuring a balance between speed and safety, and reducing risk factors are considered to play a significant role in improving this process for organizations. It is suggested that strengthening the incident reporting culture can support hurry work with an instructive approach rather than punitive punishment.

The Hurry-up syndrome reveals the invisible risk of modern aviation. While technological systems are evolving, the human component, under pressure to speed and efficiency, remains the most fragile link in the safety chain. The aircraft accidents examined in this study, although on different platforms, reflect the fact that time pressure is the greatest enemy of safety. In this context, safety culture manifests itself not only as a set of rules but also as a response to the question of how quickly one can act. A safe aviation system must have an organizational structure that resists time pressure, learns, and draws lessons from mistakes.

This study is limited to three accident reports. Therefore, the findings are limited in terms of generalizability. While qualitative document analysis allows for a deeper understanding of the cause and effect relationships of events, it does not offer the possibility of quantitative generalization. Furthermore, since accident reports are based on secondary data, data bias and limitations related to the internal standards of aviation authorities must also be considered. The wording in the reports may not fully reflect the socio-cultural context of the events. Another limitation of the study is the exclusion of other operational areas such as ground crews and passenger services. Future research could examine the effects of Hurry-up syndrome on processes such as airport ground services, cargo operations, or emergency management. Additionally, quantitative research using survey methods and simulation applications could directly measure the cognitive effects of time pressure stemming from Hurry-up syndrome, thus supporting these findings.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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